

The background of the image shows a modern building with a grid of windows and the 'TU Delft' logo on its facade. In the foreground, there are branches of cherry blossoms in full bloom, with pink flowers and green leaves. The sky is a clear, light blue.

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Abstract Titles and Authors

FRAM ANALYSIS OF THE RECOVERY PROCESS AFTER A NATECH EVENT	4
TRANSFORM: HOW RESONANCE WORKS IN FRAM	7
HIDEKI NOMOTO	7
FUNCTIONAL RESONANCE ANALYSIS METHOD (FRAM): A METHOD TO MAP WORK IN COMMUNITY RETAIL PHARMACIES.....	8
SHIYING MAI, KATHERINE G. MOORE, AARON M. GILSON, JAMIE A. STONE, MARIA E. BERBAKOV, EMILY L. HOFFINS, RUTUJA GADGIL, STEPHANIE M. RESENDIZ, JAMES H. FORD II, MICHELLE A. CHUI	8
FRAMALYSE: AN OPEN TOOL TO QUANTITATIVELY ANALYZE AND EVALUATE THE CHARACTERISTICS OF MODELS DERIVED BY THE FUNCTIONAL RESONANCE ANALYSIS METHOD	12
NIKLAS GRABBE & YIRAN DU.....	12
FROM PAPER TO RUNWAY: HOW THE FRAM ALLOWS RESONATING WITH REALITY IN AIRPORT OPERATIONS	16
MANUEL LOMBARDI, ANDREA MONTARULI, FRANCESCO SIMONE, RICCARDO PATRIARCA	16
ASSESSING THE PROCEDURES REGARDING CAVITATION INCEPTION ON NAVAL VESSELS DURING A MULTI-DAY ANTI-SUBMARINE WARFARE EXERCISE	20
JULIAN STEINKE ¹ , ROBERT VAN DE KETTERIJ ¹ , HENK DE WEERD ² , GUIDO P.H. BAND ²	20
INVISIBLE WORKERS, VISIBLE RISKS - ANALYZING THE COMPLEXITIES AND DANGERS OF GARBAGE COLLECTORS' WORK IN RIO DE JANEIRO WITH FRAM	22
JOSUÉ E. MAIA FRANÇA	22
TESTING THE APPLICABILITY OF FRAM FOR BETTER UNDERSTANDING AND IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE AND DESIGN OF LEGAL CONTRACT PREPARATION.....	24
JOHN KUNZLER ¹ , AND DAVID SLATER ²	24
SEMANTICAL CHALLENGES IN FRAM WHILE DEVELOPING THE FRAMIFIER	27
PIETER W. G. BOTS, ARIE ADRIAENSEN	27
REDESIGN OR SUSTAIN? CASE STUDY COMPARISON BETWEEN FRAM AND IDEF0 IN MEDICATION ADMINISTRATION ON A HOSPITAL WARD	31
JACO A.S. TRESFON, ANJA BRUNSVELD-REINDERS, KISRTEEN LANGEVELD, JAAP F. HAMMING	31
FRAM COMBINED WITH ABSTRACTION HIERARCHY TO ALLEVIATE GRANULARITY ISSUES IN PROCESS MODELLING	35
BJÖRN VISSER ¹ , ARIE ADRIAENSEN ²	35
DETECTING AND INCORPORATING BETWEEN-STAKEHOLDER VARIABILITY IN WORK-AS-DONE FRAM VISUALISATIONS: TWO CASE STUDIES IN HEALTHCARE	40
N.M. LUIJCKS	40
FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF SKILL REQUIREMENTS FOR REMOTE OPERATION CENTER (ROC) OPERATORS IN MARITIME CONTEXTS.....	44
TAKAYUKI HIROSE, HIDEKI NOMOTO, YASUTAKA MICHUURA	44
FUNCTIONAL PATTERNS FROM INSTANTIATIONS.....	45
DOUG SMITH, MARAL NEGARI	45

Tuesday, 13th of May

FRAMily 2025

Day 1

FRAMily 2025

Session 1

Session chair: Doug Smith | Memorial University of Newfoundland

FRAM ANALYSIS OF THE RECOVERY PROCESS AFTER A NATECH EVENT

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Keywords: Natech, post-accident-phases, FRAM, resilience curve

Introduction: In industrial areas where significant quantities of hazardous materials are handled, natural hazards can trigger severe technological accidents, known as Natech events [1], involving fires, explosions, toxic dispersions, and environmental contamination [2]. The frequency of these accidents is rising due to both the increasing occurrence of extreme natural events, driven by climate change, and the growing vulnerability of industrial installations deriving from their expansion, increased complexity, and interconnectivity [3]. The complexity of these scenarios, where industries, infrastructure, and communities may be simultaneously affected, necessitates a holistic approach to manage both the immediate impacts and the long-term consequences of such events.

In the chemical and process industry, conventional approaches for the management of major technological accidents relies on Quantitative Risk Assessment (QRA) techniques, such as fault tree and event tree analysis, which primarily focus on identifying and quantifying the severity of accident scenarios and their likelihood [2]. However, the main focus of these methods relies on the quantification of consequences to humans (typically considering the death), and these fall short in capturing system performance after disruptions and the long-term consequences of Natech accidents extending beyond humans. To address these limitations, resilience-based approaches have been introduced in the framework of Natech management [4]. In particular, quantitative assessment methodologies based on resilience curve analysis (i.e., representation of system performance over time) have gained a growing interest in recent years, as for example the approaches proposed by Caputo et al. [5] and Chen et al [6]. These approaches play a crucial role in evaluating the effectiveness of resilience measures and post-accident strategies aimed at minimizing downtime. However, these analyses are often hindered by knowledge gaps in defining the activities involved in the post-accident phases [4], which usually include an adaptation phase and a recovery phase. In the adaptation phase the plant remains shutdown, and activities as cleanup and inspection are carried out. Then, in the recovery phase restoration activities begin, and systems performance gradually improves as works progress. The knowledge gaps in the activities involved in those phases introduce

uncertainty in the mathematical modeling of the performance of the system during the post-accident phases. Therefore, a systematic investigation of the key activities involved in post-accident phases is essential for the development of reliable assessment tools for the evaluation of the performance of the system during adaptation and recovery phases following a Natech accident.

Methodology: The present study contributes to addressing these knowledge gaps by systematically mapping adaptation and recovery activities following a Natech accident. Among the available methods for studying interactions within complex-heterogeneous systems (e.g., STAMP, EAST), the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) was adopted since it enables the detailed description of complex interactions among human, technical, and organizational components involved in the adaptation and recovery phases following a Natech event. Moreover, the possibility to enrich the FRAM model through expert interviews helps to overcome the limitations posed by the poor knowledge that workers and organizations may have on the activities involved in the post-accident phases of such Natech scenarios, where industries, infrastructure, and communities may be simultaneously affected.

Figure 1 presents an overview of the methodology applied in this study, which is based on the semi-quantitative approach for FRAM quantification proposed by Patriarca et al. [7].

1) FRAM model development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1) Preliminary FRAM model based on documentary study 1.2) Update FRAM model based on open-ended interviews 1.3) Update FRAM model based on semi-structured interviews 1.4) Completeness and consistency check
2) Quantification of system performance variability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1) Definition of discrete probability distribution for output variability
3) Aggregation of performance variability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1) Definition of damping and amplification factor 3.2) Definition of different scenarios 3.3) Monte Carlo
4) Identification of critical couplings and functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.1) Calculation of criticality index for couplings and function 4.2) Ranking of critical function

Figure 1. Summary of the main steps applied in the study.

Results: Step 1 involved identifying the functions relevant to the post-accident phases following a Natech event and developing the corresponding FRAM model. This began with the construction of a preliminary description of the activities involved in the adaptation and recovery phases, based on a review of multiple incident reports publicly available on company websites. These reports detail the sequence of actions taken from accident extinguishment to the resumption of normal operations. To ensure coverage of a broad range of Natech scenarios, reports were selected from various industrial sectors handling hazardous materials—such as oil and gas, power generation, and chemical processing—and included different types of natural hazards (i.e., Great East Japan Earthquake, Hurricane Katrina, and a storm surge flooding).

Next, the preliminary FRAM model was evaluated by seven experts with strong backgrounds in Natech events and chemical process safety. The analysis aimed to develop a generalized FRAM model, with the focus on providing a generalized description of the system by identifying the main functions and connections common to all companies, while avoiding detailed descriptions of specific functions that may only apply to particular plants. Consequently, a large number of respondents was not considered necessary, and seven was deemed sufficient—well above the minimum number of

respondents recommended by Cooke and Goossens [8] to obtain significant results from expert elicitation studies. The model validation was conducted through a three-round interview process. In the first round, open-ended interviews helped identify functions requiring further detail. In the second round, semi-structured interviews were used to refine and adjust the model. In the third round, experts were presented with several scenarios—based on past Natech events and derived from the developed FRAM model—to assess its completeness. Final refinements were then made, and a consistency check was performed.

In steps 2 and 3 of the methodology, a semi-quantitative approach was adopted [7] aiming to systematically assess function and aggregate performance variabilities. To collect the necessary data, focus groups were conducted with the same experts who participated in verifying the FRAM model. These sessions were used to elicit necessary semi-quantitative scores and define discrete probability distributions for function variability in terms of timing and precision. Table 1 reports the scales used to turn expert opinions into quantitative data. In parallel, the scenario performance conditions that influence each function were defined based on the natural hazard-related disturbances identified in the documentary analysis from Step 1.

Table 1. Variability score adopted in this study with respect to time and precision.

	Variability
Timing	On time (1), Too early (2), Too late (3), Not at all (4)
Precision	Precise (1), Acceptable (2), Imprecise (3), Wrong (4)

In Step 3, Monte Carlo simulation was employed to model the aggregation of variability and calculate the Variability Priority Number (VPN) distribution for each function coupling.

Step 4 focused on identifying critical functions and couplings based on threshold criteria, with the objective of highlighting elements that exhibit a higher potential for functional resonance in Natech accidents compared to conventional High Impact Low Probability (HILP) technological accidents. Specifically, for each coupling, a VPN threshold was established using the maximum VPN value observed in baseline operational scenarios—i.e., those where natural hazard-induced disturbances are not present.

Conclusion: The analysis led to the identification of a comprehensive set of 21 functions and 94 potential couplings, forming the basis for a recovery activity network that can support resilience curve analysis of post-accident phases. Furthermore, the quantification of system variabilities enabled the identification of critical functions and couplings that require greater attention in Natech accident management, as they differ notably from those observed in conventional HILP accidents. For instance, functions such as “Restore utility systems” and “Restore storage capacity” exhibited high variability when large-scale natural events—such as earthquakes—were involved, primarily due to their interdependencies with external suppliers. These findings emphasize the importance of developing specialized assessment tools for evaluating the post-accident phases of Natech scenarios.

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TRANSFORM: HOW RESONANCE WORKS IN FRAM

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Keywords: **Fourier Transform, Quantification of Variability**

Introduction: As Hollnagel and Slater wrote in “A basic handbook on how to use the FRAM” [1], FRAM was proposed to show “that the variability of two or more functions can coincide and thereby either be dampened or amplified”. In other words, resonance among functions increases or decreases the variability of the output of sociotechnical systems. Therefore, for simulating the resonance among functions, it is essential to quantify the variability in both dampened or amplified way during propagation between functions. However, if we use only a “variability” number for quantification of the resonance, each function must have its own unique variability number which amplifies or dampens the previous function’s variability such as 1.05 for a human function and 0.56 for a machine function. This way of using a unique variability number of each function for calculation would lead to the myth that human functions always increase variability while machine functions always decrease variability, hence human functions should be replaced by machines to stabilize a system. But looking at many sociotechnical systems around us, we can easily find systems which are stabilized by human help such as human-operator-assisted automation factories. So, we need to find a method to calculate a variability number not merely multiplying or adding variability numbers directly. In this presentation, it is proposed to represent a function’s variability by frequency and amplitude of a functional wave. The frequency represents precision of time, while amplitude represents precision of quality. For example, the lowest variability machine such as an atomic clock has super high frequency & super low amplitude while a high variability human movement has very low frequency & very high amplitude.) Two functions will resonate by way of mixing two waves. In this quantification scheme,

high-variability human function (high amplitude & low frequency) could increase or decrease the variability depending on the shape of the input waves (such as sin curve can be neutralized by cos curve), which means a human function is not always a variability amplifier even though the variability itself is high. For calculating resonance among functions, Digital Fourier Transform (DFT) was implemented using FMI. In the demo, the logic is described how functions with high variability (typically performed by human) can either dampen or amplify the output variability from upstream functions. By this, it is aimed to show how humans can play important roles to stabilize systems, and that hasty automation not only fails to fulfill the required performance but also could worsen the situation in some cases.

Methods: FMI demonstration will be presented to show how Digital Fourier Transform (DFT) method is implemented to calculate the resonance quantification among functions. Each FRAM function is implemented with DFT for analyzing a complicated mixed wave by decomposing it into simple component waves using Fourier Transform method, while reconstructing a complex wave from component waves using Inverse Fourier Transform method.

Results and Discussion: FMI-DFT demo will show case studies how resonance contributes to dampen or amplify variability. Especially, it will be shown how human function with high variability can successfully dampen the variability from upstream machine functions.

Conclusion: Contrary to an automation myth, human functions in socio-technical systems do not merely destabilize a system's output: in many cases, they significantly contribute to its stability. In this presentation, the reasons and mechanism for this will be described.

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FUNCTIONAL RESONANCE ANALYSIS METHOD (FRAM): A METHOD TO MAP WORK IN COMMUNITY RETAIL PHARMACIES

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Keywords: pharmacy workflow, resilience in healthcare

Introduction: Healthcare, a complex socio-technical system, with dynamic interactions between humans, organizations, technology, and the environment[1], faces a myriad of complex challenges that require robust and adaptive responses, especially in community retail pharmacy settings. Community retail pharmacists significantly impact primary care by ensuring safe medication use, yet often encounter system challenges such as volatile work demands, inconsistent expectations from and engagement with patients and caregivers, and a lack of recognition from employers regarding the

pharmacists' operations under challenging and variable conditions [2, 3]. Addressing these challenges is critical for safe and effective pharmacy practice, as persistent operational strains can compromise both patient care and pharmacist well-being. Traditional research often employed linear analytical models that fail to capture the dynamic and complex nature of pharmacy operations, providing inadequate for addressing the nuances of pharmacists' cognitive work and decision-making processes, which are vital for effective patient care [4, 5]. Recognizing these limitations, this study advocates a comprehensive approach to visualize the intricate interactions and dependencies of prescription dispensing workflow. By mapping out process—enhance understanding of pharmacy staff's ability to anticipate, adapt to, and recover from disruptions—it provides a view that captures decision-making and adaptations made by pharmacy staff, which are often overlooked in traditional, linear research approaches.

Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) is a tool deconstructs complex systems by mapping processes, identifying essential activities and interrelations, and examining variabilities that affect outcomes, thereby enhancing the efficiency, safety, and support of healthcare work [6]. Community pharmacies, with their socio-technical nature and high-demand service environments, will benefit. Each function with FRAM is represented as a hexagon, detailing its interactions through the analysis of inputs, outputs, preconditions, resources, controls, and time. By identifying all operational steps and decision-making points, FRAM aids in pinpointing variabilities and gaps that may affect performance and medication safety, thereby enhancing resilience.

This research uses FRAM to visualize and analyze the prescription dispensing processes in community retail pharmacies. Focusing on socio-technical complexities and system resiliency identified via FRAM, we aim to create a practical and sustainable system changes for safer medication practices. These changes will be implemented in a community pharmacy to determine their effectiveness in improving system workflow, resilience, and medications safety outcomes.

Methods: Data collection included field observations and semi-structured interviews. Trained observers conducted three rounds of six-hour long observations at two distinct pharmacy settings within the same healthcare organization, for a total of 36 hours, capturing a comprehensive view of the pharmacy's daily activities. Observers meticulously noted who performed each task, as well as when, where, and how these tasks were completed. An initial FRAM model was developed based on these observations from two different researchers. This model was iteratively refined through communication between the researchers and the observers to ensure a thorough understanding of the documented tasks. Information from interviews with two pharmacists validated and further refined the FRAM model.

Results and Discussion: The FRAM model identified 53 distinct functions within the pharmacy's prescription dispensing process (Figure 1). Functions connected by the red lines signify critical steps in the core process, from receiving the prescription to the prescription is ready for patient pickup. Beyond the core process, to allows for the adaptation to meet diverse patient needs and system demands, the system also incorporates multiple feedback loops and alternative paths, reflecting the dynamic and sometimes non-linear nature of pharmacy operations. For example, blue hexagons indicate how prescription how prescriptions can be received—such as phone, paper, digital, or existing prescriptions—each leading into the system through different routes. Yellow hexagons outline the insurance verification process. This stage involves multiple pathways, including potential interactions with internal systems for prior authorization, external organizations like insurance companies, societal elements such as discount programs, or directly with patients agreeing to out-of-pocket payments. Other colors within the model also emphasize the comprehensive and interconnected structure of the system.

Figure 1 Prescription Dispensing FRAM

Conclusion: This study employs FRAM to analyze prescription dispensing processes in community retail pharmacies, which demonstrate that community pharmacy workflow is not linear. Unlike conventional models that offer simplified views, FRAM's comprehensive visualizations reveal intricate process interconnections and the complexities of operational dynamics. This approach enhances the understanding of how each component within the system interacts, which is crucial for identifying potential points of failure and areas for improvement.

Additionally, FRAM's capacity to incorporate temporal components offers significant value, particularly in environments where staff cannot control time demands. By detailing interactions between functions, FRAM pinpoints operational steps and decision-making points, which can further allow us to identify variabilities and gaps that might compromise performance and medication safety. This methodological innovation not only promises improvements in pharmacy workflow and medication safety outcomes, but also fill a critical gap in current research and practice and providing a robust framework for analyzing healthcare delivery systems. The strategic implementation of FRAM is expected to foster practical and sustainable system changes, enhancing medication safety and system resilience in community pharmacies.

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FRAMily 2025

Session 2

Session leader - FRAM software developments: Niklas Grabbe | TU
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FRAMALYSE: AN OPEN TOOL TO QUANTITATIVELY ANALYZE AND EVALUATE THE CHARACTERISTICS OF MODELS DERIVED BY THE FUNCTIONAL RESONANCE ANALYSIS METHOD

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Keywords: resilience engineering, sociotechnical system, complexity, safety management, software

Introduction: As modern socio-technical systems become increasingly complex, there is a growing need for innovative risk and safety management models and methods. The Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) is a recent approach designed to address this complexity. Interest is rising in expanding the capabilities of software tools that support FRAM analyses. Four well-known examples of FRAM-related tools are the FRAM Model Visualizer, the FRAM Model Interpreter, myFRAM, and DynaFRAM. These tools aid in modeling, simulation, visualization, and interpretation of system variabilities. However, they often lack effective practical analysis and evaluation of a FRAM model's characteristics as well as communication of analysis results. To address this gap, this presentation introduces a new open software tool—FRAMalyse [1]. Developed to enhance the quantitative analysis and evaluation of FRAM models, FRAMalyse is particularly useful for managing the complexity of large-scale FRAM models. This initial version aims to empower practitioners and decision-makers to explore FRAM models systematically, efficiently, and effectively, potentially increasing the adoption and usability of FRAM across different domains and industries. The presentation explains the functionalities of FRAMalyse, provides application purposes, and gives an outlook for possible enhancements in the future.

FRAMalyse – Functionalities and application purposes: FRAMalyse supports the analysis of steps three and four in FRAM, facilitating the visualization and interpretation of system variabilities and empowering practitioners and decision-makers to use FRAM effectively in practice. FRAMalyse is developed by Matlab App Designer as a free Standalone Desktop version for Windows environments (see Fig. 1). It is interfaced with FMV by importing the required FRAM model data in the form of Excel files. More specifically, FRAMalyse allows:

- Defining, editing, searching, and sorting functions in a tabular way with a detailed description of function type, agent, abstraction level/stage, and variability
- Calculating quantitative metrics representing variability, interaction, and complexity of functions and couplings (following the quantitative approach by [2])
- Calculating Monte-Carlo simulation to identify critical paths of variable couplings
- Representing the FRAM model instantiation as a network in a grid assigned to agents and abstraction/space-time levels enriched by upstream and downstream functions information
- Assessing and visualizing model characteristics, interrelationships, and frequencies of network parameters
- Defining risk functions and visualizing the global system variability and risk distribution over agent and abstraction levels and function types
- Assigning and visualizing risk functions along interaction and variability in a Functional Variability System Resonance Matrix
- Importing the model and instantiation data and exporting tables and images

FRAMalyse can be applied for a wide variety of purposes. First, it facilitates the comprehension of the characteristics of a FRAM model or its instantiation to get a holistic overview by providing standardized descriptive information. Second, it supports the analysis of variability, centrality, and couplings to identify spots of functional resonance and adaptive capacity, or critical paths, which can be used as leverage points to intervene in the system. Third, it enables the comparison of different scenarios in terms of what-if analysis or differences between work-as-done and work-as-imagined. This can be done globally regarding the entire system or subparts or on a fine-grain level regarding individual functions. Also, it offers the possibility to identify interaction patterns that recurrently occur over several instantiations.

Figure 1. Overview of the main user interfaces of FRAMalyse.

Results and Discussion: FRAMalyse strengthens the computational capabilities of FRAM, which makes the FRAM more actionable for real-world purposes, particularly when facing large-scale systems. The current version of FRAMalyse has already undergone alpha-testing with peers, which helped evaluate its initial value and ease of use. In the near future, a beta test with international safety and FRAM experts will be conducted to explore additional potential features and approaches, aiming to refine interfaces and enhance the user experience. We are confident that FRAMalyse represents an essential step toward establishing a foundational platform integrated with FMV to facilitate FRAM's practical and actionable application across various socio-technical systems, guiding analysis, interpretation, and communication in real-world settings.

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FRAMily 2025

Session 3

Session chair: Hideki Nomoto | JAMMS

FROM PAPER TO RUNWAY: HOW THE FRAM ALLOWS RESONATING WITH REALITY IN AIRPORT OPERATIONS

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Keywords: Resilience engineering, complex system analysis, airport operations management, operational variability

Introduction: Along with the continuous development of civil aviation, airports have gradually acquired the traits of a complex socio-technical systems [1]. They consist of an intertwined set of social and technical actors interacting with each other, and adapting to continuously changing environments and unforeseen challenges [2]. Even if highly regulated, and considered an “ultra-safe system”, airport processes are frequently subjected to discrepancies between what is described in organizational documents (Work-As-Imagined) and the actual work practices carried out during everyday operations (Work-As-Done).

To highlight these deviations, this work leverages a structured and systematic approach based on the FRAM, applied to a specific type of airport activity.

In literature, there are contributions exploring the application of the FRAM within airport operations, such as [1] wherein the authors propose to evaluate the level of safety resilience loss of airport operations. Moreover, in [3] the authors aim to evaluate the airport passenger and cabin luggage security check process using the FRAM. However, to the best of our knowledge, there are no contributions leveraging the FRAM to identify the misalignment between Work-As-Done and Work-As-Imagined in airport maintenance activities. Accordingly, this approach is tested on a specific type of maintenance activity at Airport X referred to as “minor activities”, which refers to those programmable interventions of ordinary maintenance that do not require any design activity but may have an impact on the safety of airside airport operations.

Method: The study leverages the FRAM to model airport maintenance activities.

More in detail, the study involves the analysis of all the available documents related to activities of interest for the case study at hand, starting from the conduction of a Hierarchical Task Analysis [4].

This leads to the identification of core task steps, according to the documentation, which are the foundation for the development of the FRAM framework of the Work-As-Imagined.

Once a clear understanding of the process at hand and its criticalities (i.e., potential points of interest in the study) is established, a series of semi-structured interviews with front-line personnel are conducted. This investigative phase, supported by on-site observations of the activities of interest, is crucial to further explore the criticalities emerged from the analysis of the Work-As-Imagined. The combination of semi-structured interviews and on-site observations leads to the definition of a new FRAM model reflecting how everyday operations actually take place, specifically the FRAM framework of the Work-As-Done.

With the knowledge of the activities acquired up to this point, it is possible to identify instantiations of interest. These are used to conduct a systemic analysis to evaluate and prioritize the criticalities emerged from the deviations revealed by the comparison of the two FRAM models obtained.

Accordingly, the main contribution of this method lies in addressing processes shortcomings emerged from the Work-As-Imagined and Work-As-Done comparison, by proposing targeted recommendations, showcasing the ability of the approach to deliver useful operational outcomes.

Results and Discussion: As mentioned earlier, the approach is applied to a specific type of maintenance activity at Airport X, leading to the identification of a finite number of instantiations of interest. Specifically, exemplary results are presented for just one of the Work-As-Done FRAM instantiations (i.e., commissioning of the site after maintenance activity completion), as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Work-As-Done FRAM instantiation representing the commissioning of the site after completion of the maintenance activity. Please note that each color refers to a different actor, and the aspects circled in red represent non-connected aspects.

The FRAM model illustrated in Figure 1 shows that more than half of the considered functions are either highly variable or absent in the Work-As-Done representation, showcasing high inconsistencies with respect to Work-As-Imagined.

This abstract presents one simplified research outcome, in which the focus can be placed on the task of properly signing the specific document required to formally testify the site's operability after the completion of maintenance work. Ideally, this task should be performed at the end of the maintenance activity; however, due to operational urge in daily operations, it is often carried out a priori or later, at an entirely different time. This inconsistency may implicitly jeopardize the safety of operations and, if an unwanted event occurs, could lead to repercussion for the front-line personnel involved.

Conclusion: This research demonstrates the applicability of the FRAM to compare the Work-As-Imagined and the Work-As-Done in airport maintenance activities to identify process shortcomings and to generate targeted recommendations. Specifically, the significance of the method in the aviation context was recently confirmed by its inclusion among the methods recommended by ICAO, as part of the Safety Management Implementation [5].

Several inconsistencies were detected in the maintenance activity analyzed (i.e., "minor activities"). For instance, there is a poor comprehensive sharing of a structured document for planning and monitoring airside maintenance activities, along with little if any practical guidelines for its use. Moreover, roles and responsibilities of personnel involved in maintenance activities are not always clearly defined. This thus led to a set of recommendations to enhance the safety and efficiency of airport maintenance operations. This research aims to demonstrate the broader applicability of this approach, which can be ideally extended to any kind of airport process.

Further research could explore the identification of meta-patterns as recurring drivers in the comparison of Work-As-Imagined and Work-As-Done. This might pave the way to obtain an approach able to systematically address deviations from Work-As-Imagined and Work-As-Done.

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ASSESSING THE PROCEDURES REGARDING CAVITATION INCEPTION ON NAVAL VESSELS DURING A MULTI-DAY ANTI-SUBMARINE WARFARE EXERCISE

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Keywords: Socio-technical systems, Human Factors, Cavitation, Anti-submarine warfare, Navy, Human-machine interaction, FRAM

Introduction: Cavitation describes the vaporization of water due to a low pressure caused by the movement of a solid object through it [1], [2]. Propellers often cause cavitation, which creates unstable trails of bubbles, that are trailing the blades. These bubbles will implode, causing a shockwave, which creates a significant amount of sound on a broad spectrum [3]. Cavitation at the propeller is one of the strongest sources of underwater radiated noise caused by motorized ships [4]. There are both ecological and military needs for minimizing radiated noise and thus for avoiding cavitation[5], [6], [7], [8], [9].

The current study is part of the Cavitation Inception Speed CONtrol (CISCON) project aimed at understanding and preventing cavitation in surface ships, focussing on a navy frigate. Preventing cavitation is essential for crews on naval vessels, as the underwater radiated noise caused by cavitation can be used to detect the ship and attack it[6], [8]. As this prevention process requires the crew of a vessel to act on cavitation information, it is necessary to chart the current cavitation-related processes on board. This study compares the work as imagined and the work as done for the cavitation-related tasks of the crew on the bridge. The goals are to investigate how the current system on board works, to identify possible indicators for brittleness, and to suggest possible solutions for integrating cavitation monitoring.

Methods: We conducted a Functional Resonance Analysis based on observations on board an anti-submarine warfare vessel during a two-week anti-submarine exercise of a NATO fleet and compared the intended procedures to the actual situation on board. The model of the work as imagined was gathered during observations on board and by recording officers in training in simulator exercises [10].

Results and Discussion: In total, 30 functions were identified. The functions were then grouped to the actor on board that executes them, thus the OOW, lookout, CO, sonar operator, and the helm. In addition, some functions have been classified as systemic functions that are being executed by the joint cognitive system at large. With eleven functions, the OOW executed the most functions, six of which exhibited significant variability. The generated FRAM model shows a complex network of functions to be executed by the officer of the watch, who often utilizes their crewmates in the ship to share the workload. Although these workarounds are supporting the system, their successful execution relies on preconditions, that are not guaranteed to be in place. These preconditions are not part of sanctioned training and checking whether or not these preconditions are in place is based on trust, not on official qualifications. For example, any function executed by the helm is not present in the work as imagined.

Conclusion: The procedures of the work as intended are being used, but the system they create is brittle. Several workarounds in the work as done have been identified that are being used to relieve the strain on the system. The watch officer has the highest workload and frequently utilizes their crew to offload tasks. This lowers their workload, but potentially causes problems that the overall system cannot mitigate. This study shows the necessity of a cavitation information system on the bridge to support the watch officer and their crew.

Figure - FRAM model of the observed system.

Note: Blue functions are executed by the lookout, green by the OOW, red by the CO, grey by the sonar operator, black by the helm, and purple by the system at large. Sine waves indicate functions with variable performance.

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INVISIBLE WORKERS, VISIBLE RISKS - ANALYZING THE COMPLEXITIES AND DANGERS OF GARBAGE COLLECTORS’ WORK IN RIO DE JANEIRO WITH FRAM

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Keywords: Risk Assessment, Human Factors, Safety Engineering, FRAM

Introduction: The work of urban garbage collectors is essential to public health and environmental sustainability, yet it remains an often invisible and high-risk occupation. In Rio de Janeiro, garbage collectors perform their duties by collecting and disposing of waste while precariously positioned on the back of moving garbage trucks. Despite the critical nature of their work, they face hazardous conditions, including exposure to biological and chemical contaminants, physical strain, and traffic-related dangers. This study applies the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) to systematically analyze the complexity and risks associated with garbage collection, mapping the systemic interactions that influence worker safety and performance.

Methods: This research employs a qualitative methodology based on a review of technical studies, structured interviews, field observations and regulatory documents related to the occupational hazards faced by garbage collectors. Using FRAM modeling, the study identifies key functional interactions within the waste collection process, focusing on how performance variability influences safety outcomes. The analysis includes factors such as the design of garbage trucks, the physical demands of lifting and handling waste, exposure to sharp and hazardous materials, and the influence of environmental conditions.

Results and Discussion: The results highlight the dynamic and interdependent nature of garbage collection work, revealing how variability in operational conditions can contribute to both resilience and failure within the system. The study shows that the absence of adequate safety infrastructure, coupled with high physical demands and precarious employment conditions, increases the likelihood of occupational injuries and long-term health issues. These findings emphasize the need for improved safety measures, such as better vehicle design, revised collection protocols, and enhanced worker training programs.

Conclusion: This research contributes to the broader discussion on urban sanitation labor policies by providing a structured analysis of work practices through the FRAM framework. It underscores the pressing need for regulatory improvements that integrate worker-centered safety strategies. By offering a non-linear understanding of the risks faced by garbage collectors, this study aims to inform policymakers and industry stakeholders about necessary interventions to enhance worker safety and operational efficiency in urban waste management systems.

Figure 1 – Example of garbage collection by trucks in Rio de Janeiro.

Figure 2 – Example of garbage collection by motorcycles in Rio de Janeiro.

TESTING THE APPLICABILITY OF FRAM FOR BETTER UNDERSTANDING AND IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE AND DESIGN OF LEGAL CONTRACT PREPARATION

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Keywords: Legal Contracts, FRAM, WAI, WAD

Introduction: In this study we focus on the potential application of Functional Resonance Analysis Method [1] in the domain of legal practice work design and improvement, in the specific instance of drafting of commercial contracts.

Why is this relevant now?

Law firms are increasingly adopting generative and non-generative artificial intelligence decision support or autonomous processes (cite) to deliver legal processes.

Applying modern safety thinking to minimise known legal process weaknesses at design stage is considered likely to support reliability and assurance in relation to the adoption of artificial intelligence technology. In turn this provides an opportunity to reduce performance variability, perhaps in turn delivering savings in losses and insurance costs. FRAM and the FMV visualisation tool offer a new lens to create insights and interventions by understanding the interdependencies between parties in conducting legal work.

Gap in existing research

FRAM is an increasingly cited tool in different industries [2], but with the exception of aviation safety and medical practice, little evidence of study is apparent in other professional domains. In legal practice, there are various professional routines and approaches where core processes have remained largely consistent for 40 or 50 years, and there is long run error data which can potentially be matched against model performance, and publishing research is likely to drive familiarity enabling studies.

Research questions

Does the FRAM approach appear to be applicable and potentially effective in describing operation and potential re-design of legal contact preparation?

Methods: A test model of the FRAM visualiser was built with nominal error probabilities for different factors. The various functions involved in generating a commercial agreement in a law firm workplace were considered and modelled in the tool to produce a visualisation.

Notional error rates and probabilities were assigned to the various aspects to create outcomes and a rough “risk assessment”.

Results and Discussion: The instantiation of the FRAM visualiser model created suggests how error probability can build up through interactions and constraints and enables modelling of non-linear assumptions modifying the interaction of the “aspects”

Conclusion:

How these findings contribute to the field of risk and safety management for law firms

FRAM can initially be difficult to grasp, and even safety specialists have admitted they “do not understand it at all” while accepting even at that point in time [3] that “it was “a powerful instrument – in the right hands” [4]

The instantiation developed sets a basis for discussion of the FRAM approach that can be understood at law firm practitioner level to improve the value and learning from work studies using FRAM. This could be applied for example in areas where human/machine interfaces are likely to increase in sophistication and artificial intelligence applications also taking a leading role in delivery.

Understanding variation between work “as imagined” and “as done” creates the possibility of more efficient and workplaces which acknowledge the value of departures from work “as imagined” and mitigate the risk that broad brush interventions do not taking account of those departures contributing to overall existing performance. This is especially important when considering how intelligent automation might be applied, if assurance is to be maintained while delivering efficiency.

The instantiation will be socialised with practitioners and proposed for field study to test assumptions and identify opportunities for safer practice.

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Wednesday, 14th of May

FRAMily 2025

Day 2

FRAMily 2025

Session 4

Session chair: Rogier Woltjer | Lund University

SEMANTICAL CHALLENGES IN FRAM WHILE DEVELOPING THE FRAMIFIER

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Keywords: FRAMifier, Semantical challenges

Introduction: An open-source graphical editor and simulation tool in support of the Functional Resonance Analysis Method called the FRAMifier [1], [2] was developed by Pieter Bots, based on discussions with Arie Adriaensen at Delft University of Technology. The FRAMifier software is open source (MIT license), and coded in plain HTML, CSS and JavaScript so that it runs in any modern browser. The application aims to provide an intuitive user interface that enforces syntactical and semantical soundness of the FRAM model being constructed and facilitates analysis of its instantiation. This aim entails that not only the syntax but also the semantics of the FRAM graphical notation must be well-defined. This abstract addresses four semantic issues to be discussed with the FRAMily 2025 participants. Outcomes can then be accounted for in subsequent FRAMifier development iterations.

According to the syntax of the FRAM notation as set out by Hollnagel [3], a FRAM model consists of a set of hexagon-shaped functions that are interconnected by potential couplings. Functions are characterized by six aspects, where one aspect (output) is generated based on five ‘receiving’ aspects (input, control, time, precondition, and resource). Functions represent activities and hence are named with verb phrases. Aspects represent a state or result of a function and hence are named with noun phrases that appear as labels on the interconnections. Couplings relate the output of one function to one of the five receiving aspects of a downstream function. Functions having no couplings with some downstream function are called sinks; functions having no couplings with the output of some upstream function are called sources [3]. Such functions are displayed as gray-shaded hexagons to reflect that they are the functional entry and exit points of a FRAM model that are collectively also called background functions (indicating the scope restriction of the FRAM model) [3]. This

summarizes the basic syntax of a FRAM model, on which the semantics must consequently be grounded.

Results and Discussion: The aim of the exchange with the audience at the FRAMily 2025 is to align the semantics with the theoretical underpinnings of the FRAM, and the intuitive use of the FRAMifier by affordance-driven design of its point-and-click graphical user interface, meaning that it only invites and accepts syntactically and semantically valid inputs.

We seek to interrogate these four semantic issues: (1) the logic of an abstraction hierarchy of functions, (2) the computation of aspects when instantiating a model, (3) the attribution and scope of aspects, and (4) the passing of time in the system being investigated. We pose these semantic issues as (sometimes dilemmatic) choices that have been made for the present version (v0.1.7) of the FRAMifier, so that they can be challenged in the FRAMily 2025 interrogation.

Abstraction hierarchy logic

Large FRAM models tend to become a “spaghetti” of functions and couplings that make them difficult to interpret. Patriarca et al. [4] extend the traditional FRAM model by a framework that combines a four-level abstraction hierarchy of functions with clustering by agent. The FRAMifier affords associating functions with agents and a hierarchical decomposition of functions. But the FRAMifier does not attribute a specific meaning to abstraction levels. Similar to activity decomposition in IDEF0 [5], abstraction occurs by grouping functions as subfunctions of a composite function. The subfunctions of a composite function may be either composite or elementary (i.e., having no subfunctions). When potential couplings can be defined only between elementary functions, a hierarchically structured model is functionally equivalent to its “flattened” version that comprises only the elementary functions and their couplings.

The FRAMifier imposes this constraint and also enforces that functions (elementary or composite) can be a subfunction of only one other function (its parent function). The theoretical underpinnings of FRAM contradict the philosophy of strict decomposability [6]. However, since the way in which a set of elementary functions is arranged in a hierarchy of composite functions does not alter the model or its resulting instantiations, this permits different hierarchy configurations to be applied to the same model. These configurations could be seen as alternative decompositions or views. This approach aligns with the principle of deconstruction, rather than with strict decomposition. The semantics of enabling such views and the possibility of enforcing semantic rigor while constructing them need further discussion.

Computation of aspects

Qualitative interpretation of a FRAM model follows the logic that a function generates its outputs when it is activated. This activation occurs when the function receives the output of an upstream function as input, and then only when its preconditions (if any) are satisfied, its resources (if any) are available, and its controls (if any) are provided. When a receiving aspect (i.e., ©®ⓈⓉ or CRPIT) of a function relates to multiple functions, the FRAM syntax offers no means for indicating whether all these functions need to be activated or just one. The FRAM Model Interpreter [6] resolves this by associating an Interpretation Profile with a function that specifies for its CRPIT-aspects whether all, any, or none of their potential couplings must be present.

The FRAMifier associates expressions with aspects. This affords specifying how to compute a numerical value for the output aspects of a function when the function is activated. These expressions are quite similar to those commonly used in programming languages, except that variables must be enclosed between brackets to permit the use of spaces, e.g., [Noodles covered with boiling water]. If no expressions are specified, the output aspects of a function are assumed to be true only when that

function is active. To resolve the issue of CRPIT-aspects having multiple couplings, the FRAMifier also associates expressions with the ©®ⓈⓉⓃ circles on a hexagon to specify how their values should be computed based on the values of the aspects they receive from upstream functions. Non-zero values are interpreted as true, zero as false. If no expressions are specified, a default logic is applied: the CRPIT-aspects of a function are considered to be true if they have no couplings or if all aspects on their couplings are true. Our contention is that these two ways of associating expressions with aspects provide a uniform and elegant mechanism to give the modeler full control over the activation of functions without resorting to metadata [7].

Attribution and scope of aspects

Since aspects appear (as noun phrases) on couplings, they always relate to two functions f and g. When an aspect describes a result (output) of function f, it would appear logical to attribute it to f, rather than to g, especially because it can be a receiving aspect (input, control, time, precondition or resource) of several other functions. A noun phrase should not be used to describe the output of more than one function because this would make its instantiation ambiguous. The FRAMifier imposes this constraint, but this only limits the scope of aspects in the sense that the noun phrases appearing on the couplings with functions upstream of function f can be used as variables in expressions associated with the aspects of f. Our contention is that this limitation does not restrict the capability to represent system behavior.

Time

The FRAM considers time as a special type of aspect but does not formally define its semantics. The FRAMifier keeps track of time (represented in expressions by the symbol now) by means of a point in time list. Time is reckoned in hours from the start of a simulation (now = 0) and is advanced only when computing time aspect expressions that make use of the operator after and/or until. When these operators are computed, they set points-in-time. Similar to the FRAM Model Interpreter, the FRAMifier iterates over the set of functions in cycles to see if they can be activated. At the end of each cycle, the FRAMifier advances time to the earliest point-in-time and removes it from the list. The last time a function was activated (represented by the symbol last) can be used in expressions for output aspects of that function. Thus, in the classic noodles example [7], adding after(last + [2-3 minutes]) as expression for the Tender noodles aspect will make time advance by the value computed for the aspect 2- 3 minutes before the function To stir noodles well is activated. To effectively wait for 2 to 3 minutes, the expression for this time aspect could be formulated as (2 + random) / 60 (as time is measured in hours) or alternatively 2m + random * 1m (as the FRAMifier interprets symbols like 1h15 and 20s as time constants). Adding until(last + 1m30) as expression for the Boiling water aspect will permit the function To pour boiling water until fill mark to become active only when its other receiving aspects evaluate as true within 90 seconds after the boiling water is produced. Note that logical conditions such as now > 1h15 are valid, but will not advance time, and hence evaluate as 1 (true) except when time is advanced by other expressions that do make use of after and/or until. We contend that this mechanism suffices to simulate the temporal relations between the activations of functions.

Conclusion: Interrogating the semantic choices related to the FRAM notation that are embodied in the present version of the FRAMifier software may contribute to its usability. We hope that the exchange with experts on the FRAMily 2025 platform will help verify our contentions, articulate alternative interpretations of a FRAM model, and inspire ideas for supporting such diversity with modelling options.

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REDESIGN OR SUSTAIN? CASE STUDY COMPARISON BETWEEN FRAM AND IDEF0 IN MEDICATION ADMINISTRATION ON A HOSPITAL WARD

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Keywords: Hospital ward, Medication administration

Introduction: Resilience Engineering and the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) are used to improve safety in complex sociotechnical systems like healthcare. Main argument for adopting FRAM is that healthcare systems are too complex to untangle, making it difficult to decompose the system in meaningful separate parts or functions. Instead, performance variability should be detected and assessed on its aptitude, interaction effects and potential consequences [1],[2]. One result of this is that the focus of safety is enlarged from harmful events toward structural trade-offs (e.g. efficiency, bed capacity, staffing, availability of resources) [3].

On the other hand, established modelling techniques such as Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) and Integration Definition for Function (IDEF0) have also been successfully employed in healthcare to improve safety, efficiency and workflow [4]-[7]. IDEF0 is a method to describe processes in (complex) systems to evaluate how activities are or should be organized. The argument here is that systems modelling can optimize system and process performance by using decomposition and redesign of process activities. The theoretical underpinnings from FRAM, on the other hand state that the decomposability of functional systems is a reductionist oversimplification of the reality of work systems. At the same time, FRAM and IDEF0 are similar in use and approach: both require understanding of everyday activities to model everyday performance. Both use consecutive transformative actions (activities) to map system performance, either through transformation of products or states. However, there are also different conventions applicable to both methods. For instance, functions in IDEF0 are always accompanied by a control, which always is a piece of information that directs if, how and when an activity is executed. In FRAM, control are aspects of functions that do not necessarily have to be present, and activities are principally started through 'input aspects' which are outputs of upstream activities (functions). IDEF0 makes use of different levels of abstraction to zoom-in on sub-processes, while FRAM was originally made with scale invariance. The different conventions between IDEF0 and FRAM both have unique benefits to integrate detail into the model, but leave to wonder what disadvantages exist between the modelling approaches.

Moreover, there are different principal assumptions behind both models. IDEF0 assumes that the interrelationships between key activities required to achieve a given objective can be determined following cause-effect relationships. FRAM approaches systems from principles of equivalence of success and failure, the need for approximate adjustments, emergence of outcomes and functional resonance. These different assumptions have large implications for how results should be interpreted and inform subsequent improvements. This leads to the question of under what conditions in practice each method can be employed successfully. Therefore, the aim of this study is to model a safety-critical process in hospital care and review the similarities, differences and implications of a FRAM and IDEF0 analysis for the same process. The objective of this study was to develop FRAM and IDEF0 models and compare the two for medication administration by nurses and physicians on a hospital ward.

Methods: Data was collected on a neurological/neurosurgical hospital ward of an Academic Medical Centre in the Netherlands as part of an ethnographic study. Viewpoint guiding the data collection was

the perspective and activities of nurses in the medication administration process on the ward. Collection methods included open observations during participant observations (n=6) on the ward shadowing nurses, follow-up by semi-structured interviews with nurses (n=4), physicians (n=3) and a hospital pharmacist (n=1) of varying professional experience with working on the ward. Modelling and analysis of the FRAM was done iteratively after observations and between interviews in collaboration with a research nurse from the ward. Modelling and analysis of the IDEF0 model was done using the same raw data that informed the FRAM analysis.

Results and Discussion:

FRAM Model

Construction and iterations of the FRAM provided an overview of conditional functions in the medication administration process from a nurses' viewpoint. Several points stood out, taken together in the following themes:

- **Nurses as a safety net.** Several implemented “barriers” to medication errors were present in the medication administration process, ranging from administrative and procedural barriers in the electronic patient records, toward work agreements (“four eye principle”) and distribution of error-prone tasks over shifts (night versus day/evening). Nurses act as a safety net in this process. A multitude of tactics to overcome diverging scenario’s were employed by nurses. Examples including recovering missing medication from the wards’ pharmacy, preparing intravenous medication ad-hoc, or consulting patients and/or family members if certain medicine was correctly prescribed before administration.
- **Teamwork.** The guiding principle in the work on the ward was to consult a fellow nurse when in doubt about the appropriateness of a certain prescription. Doubts arose from clinical reasoning by a nurse about the correctness of a prescription compared to clinical status of a patient and prior information about the patients’ condition. Nurses first consulted each other, before consulting a physician. Again, several tactics were employed to estimate and communicate the urgency of a question to a physician. Nurses and physician who were more familiar with each others working methods and preferences reported to have fewer disturbances in each other’s workflow.
- **Missing viewpoints.** Some viewpoints, although very relevant for the medication administration process, were difficult to incorporate in the FRAM. Nurses and physicians are the main actors in ward care medication administration. However, for physicians this process is shared between shifts within different working contexts in the hospital (e.g. prescribing medicine on the E.D., after surgery, during night-shifts) and between roles (medical specialist, surgeon, attendings, residents). Varying rotating schedules made it difficult to provide direct feedback on the one who made a prescription between nurses and physicians. Furthermore, the hospitals’ pharmacy provided several checks in ‘the background’, such as approving prescriptions before they were made visible to nurses and checking for interaction effects. Incorporating these activities would require a FRAM on another abstraction level than currently presented (i.e. nurses viewpoint).

Implications of the FRAM model are that certain functions should be enhanced to increase their likelihood of occurrence. Such include being aware of certain tactics to prevent medication errors flowing through the process, and explicitly sharing these between nurses and with new nurses. Also, the importance of clinical reasoning and thus experience in ward care and with the patient group are prominent to enhance ‘doubt’ as a function. Finally, being aware of each other’s working methods (especially between physicians and nurses).

Similarities and differences

IDEF0 in preparation. Preliminary results:

- IDEF0 requires every activity to be accompanied by a control: this state if, when or how a certain transformation should take place. In the FRAM model, control aspects remained mostly absent, although many functions in the model acted as an extra control for appropriate medication administration.
- FRAM lacks the ability to zoom-out to higher levels of abstraction without making the model overly complicated. IDEF0 however incorporates this approach to process modelling by using different levels and hard conventions in describing functions within levels.

Conclusion: The results from this study indicate that both FRAM and IDEF0 can be applied to high-risk processes in healthcare. However, the different orientations toward safety system functioning obscure new interventions for process design for FRAM, whereas IDEF0 provides redesign alternatives. Future studies using FRAM could benefit from incorporating barrier thinking through different scenarios in the modelling approach (within or between functions), whereas IDEF0 could benefit from hazard identification within or between activities

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FRAM COMBINED WITH ABSTRACTION HIERARCHY TO ALLEVIATE GRANULARITY ISSUES IN PROCESS MODELLING

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Keywords: FRAM, BPM, Abstraction Hierarchy

Motivation: FRAM in combination with Abstraction Hierarchy is proposed as an alternative for Business Process Model and Notation (BPM). FRAM Abstraction Hierarchy (AH) is used in

combination with FRAMifier as a practical FRAM modeller to defend horizontal and vertical model consistency and to increase FRAM model validity for the description of worker instructions and functional protocols.

Introduction: Business Process Model and Notation (BPM) is used to model work processes in manufacturing environments and process industries. Inevitably, understanding and describing complex work systems reduces real-world complexity through model representation [1] and excludes certain aspects of evolving contexts and work system dynamics. Often, granularity issues arise when work processes are modelled through BPM. Also, process models often lack objectivity due to inconsistent levels of detail and terminology, which complicates their usability and analysis [2]. BPM is often used as the basis for worker instructions and procedural design. However, BPM often fails to provide instruction because of mixing aspects of functional, behavioral, organizational, and informational process perspectives without necessarily making the differences between these aspects clear to the user and by confounding these aspects at different procedural abstraction levels [2].

Method: FRAM requires closing models to achieve functional consistency. This is achieved by connecting all inputs and outputs from foreground functions. This could be described as the requirement of horizontal model completeness at a given AH level in the context of this abstract. Information collected from work as done (WAD) can also be used to correct further and complement horizontal model completeness. Contrary to this horizontal element, AH [3] can be used in FRAM to achieve vertical completeness. It can also be used to achieve granularity consistency, a shortcoming in BPM described by [2]. A recently developed open-source FRAM modeler, called the FRAMifier [4], was used as proof of concept during a master thesis project to produce FRAM models with different abstraction levels in the process of shipbuilding. The case study is not covered in the results from this abstract, but the data derived from the examined real-world system can support the conference presentation.

Results and Discussion: Existing BPM models (Work-as-Intended/Imagined, WAI) and observational data (WAD) can be transformed into FRAM models. However, due to the inherent limitations of BPM models and the unstructured nature of raw observational data, it is necessary to systematically organize BPM descriptions enriched/corrected with WAD observations before they are suitable for detailed analysis and comparison. We describe below how FRAM models can be structured and enhanced using an Abstraction Hierarchy approach with the dummy model from Figure 1 below. Typically a total of five possible staggered levels of abstraction are recognized by the AH technique described in Patriarca et al. [3]. This comprises higher abstraction levels such as Functional Purpose (FP), Abstract Function (AF), and Generalized Function (GF) down to the concrete levels of Physical Functions and their Physical Forms.

Consider a given FRAM model based on a BPM description (WAI) in Figure 1 which contains functions at the three higher abstraction levels. This represents an imaginary FRAM model of a hypothetical work system.

Figure 1: Step 1 - application of AH to a BPM-inspired FRAM model with missing functions and corresponding AH level deconstruction

Initially, each function within this model is classified according to its corresponding tier in the abstraction hierarchy, based on the definitions provided by Patriarca et al. [3]. This classification produces an organized overview of existing functions across their respective tiers, as illustrated at the bottom of Figure 1. Based on a single-level BPM description, FRAM functions are first assigned to their correct AH levels, typically resulting in incomplete FRAM descriptions.

To systematically analyze and compare this work system against a complete abstraction hierarchy, it is essential to expand the current model by defining functions (including their connections) at the other abstraction tiers using means-end relationships as originally defined by Vicente [5]. The identification of functions can be restricted to the hierarchy abstraction levels under investigation, and from which functions are still missing. During this functional expansion, two scenarios may occur:

- If a function exists at a lower tier and the corresponding higher-tier function has not yet been defined, an appropriate higher-tier function must be identified or introduced. This higher-tier function should hold an effective means-end relationship to the existing lower-tier function.
- If a function exists at a higher tier without associated functions defined at the lower tiers, this higher-tier function must be elaborated into one or several lower-tier functions down to the appropriate level for the analysis under consideration. These new functions are based on a means-end relationship with the original higher-tier function.

This structured approach ensures the FRAM model identifies all the functions at the necessary abstraction levels, facilitating horizontal and vertical comprehensiveness of the model. The last step consists of providing the connections to all functions.

The top of Figure 2 contains the original work system from Figure 1 but enriched and completed at the functional purpose and abstract function levels. Subsequently, the bottom of Figure 2 shows the resulting FRAM model representations for these two distinct abstraction hierarchy levels. Each

representation independently provides a complete depiction of the given work system, enabling separate analyses.

The abstraction levels are chosen in line with the scope of the analysis. The decision for the correct AH levels is chosen by the analyst in line with the scope of the work system analysis and purpose.

Figure 2: Step 2 – completed AH level functions (vertical) and corresponding FRAM model representation

The FRAM models were made using the FRAMifier software [4]. This FRAM modelling tool allows for hierarchical FRAM function initialization. However, a current limitation of this software is the inability to present complete FRAM model representations at levels other than the top level, although lower levels can be reached by zooming in on levels below top-level functions.

Conclusion: This approach can be extended to integrate multiple perspectives of the same work system by using different abstraction hierarchy levels combined with WAD enrichment. For instance, a WAD model, typically described at a more generalized, practical level based on observations and interactions with sharp-end workers, can be systematically elevated to higher abstraction levels by aggregating these generalized functions. In contrast, WAI models usually originate from higher abstraction tiers. Consequently, by aligning the WAD model with a comparable abstraction level of the WAI model through function aggregation, a systematic and structured comparison between the two models can be effectively conducted.

The proposed method contributes to the challenges identified in Beerepoort's paper [2]. The contribution is four-fold:

- The proposed method solves for the issue of inconsistent granularity in BPM
- FRAM in general solves for the existence of independent process silo's

- The missing knowledge behind event data is made explicit through function categorization within the AH framework.
- Using this method, a systemic comparison can be made between work system perspectives. The need to separate work and recording work (digital logging) in BPM could be reduced.

Overall, an iteration was made on the work on AH by Patriarca, opening the possibilities of FRAM combined with AH towards analysis and evaluation of BPM practices.

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FRAMily 2025

Session 5

Session chair: Josué Franca | Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro

DETECTING AND INCORPORATING BETWEEN-STAKEHOLDER VARIABILITY IN WORK-AS-DONE FRAM VISUALISATIONS: TWO CASE STUDIES IN HEALTHCARE

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Keywords: Work-as-Done, Between-Stakeholder Variability

Introduction: The Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) can be used to gain insight into how a written process (Work-as-Imagined) compares to daily practice (Work-as-Done) [1]-[3]. For creating Work-as-Imagined, protocols or guidelines are mostly analysed using document analysis, e.g. [4]-[7]. For creating Work-as-Done, in most cases, data is collected from involved stakeholders. Where Work-as-Imagined can usually be captured by a few specific protocols or guidelines, is Work-as-Done far more heterogeneous due to the involvement of multiple stakeholders and multiple data sources. Some functions in Work-as-Done may be mentioned by multiple stakeholders where others by only one. However, this between-stakeholder variability in Work-as-Done is not explicitly taken into account in FRAM analyses. This variability can affect decisions in FRAM, such as deciding whether there are differences between Work-as-Imagined and Work-as-Done, and whether all functions should be included in a FRAM visualisations if some are only mentioned by one stakeholder. Rather, the Work-as-Done mostly describes the combined perspective of all stakeholders. This could lead to missing bottlenecks or possibilities for process improvement. Currently, there is no guidance or best practice in FRAM research on how to incorporate the heterogeneity within the Work-as-Done data. The objective of this study is to analyse the extent of between-stakeholder variation Work-as-Done using heatmaps, and show how it might impact decisions on differences between Work-as-Imagined and Work-as-Done.

Methods: Two FRAM studies were analysed—one on delirium diagnosis and treatment, and another on perioperative anticoagulant management in two hospitals. For Work-as-Imagined, document analysis was used. Semi-structured interviews were analysed to create Work-as-Done, with case study 1 also using observations. For each participant, an individual FRAM visualisation was created and colours were used to indicate roles within functions. A heatmap visualised how often functions were mentioned by stakeholders, based on the individual FRAM visualisation. This represented the between-stakeholder variability in Work-as-Done. The effect of excluding the functions mentioned only once by stakeholders was shown on the possible differences between Work-as-Imagined and Work-as-Done.

Results and Discussion: The heatmaps revealed that both studies show significant variation between what functions are mentioned by stakeholders. In the delirium case (1), more between-stakeholder variability can be found than in the anticoagulant management case (2). If the functions that were mentioned only once would be removed, this would impact detectable differences between Work-as-Imagined and Work-as-Done. In the delirium case, removing the functions would lead to fewer differences. In one hospital of the second case it would increase differences, whereas it would reduce differences in the other hospital. This suggests the importance of gaining insight into between-stakeholder variability and taking this factor into account when deciding on differences between Work-as-Imagined and Work-as-Done.

Awareness of differences between stakeholders could lead to useful conversation about the process, since not all stakeholders seem aware of the specific function, or perform workarounds instead. Discussing the variability with stakeholders could lead to an improved shared mental model of the process, which in turn could improve team performance [8]-[10]. This study does not provide a one-size-fits-all solution for users, but can provide a framework to validate and discuss the FRAM visualisations with stakeholders. Additionally, using these heatmaps to describe the data on which a final Work-as-Done visualisation is based, can improve the transparency on the decisions made by researchers.

Conclusion: Between-stakeholder variability in FRAM visualisations shows to what extent an overview of the process is shared across stakeholders, and can affect whether differences between Work-as-Imagined and Work-as-Done are identified. Discussing between-stakeholder variability with involved professionals can positively influence a shared understanding of the process, and reporting this variability in research can provide a transparent overview of the decisions made by researchers.

Figure 1 - Heatmap of Work-as-Done Variability on Delirium Diagnosis and Management

Figure 2 - Heatmap of Work-as-Done Variability on anticoagulants in the perioperative trajectory (hospital 1)

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Session 6

Session chair: Gesa Praetorius | VTI

FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF SKILL REQUIREMENTS FOR REMOTE OPERATION CENTER (ROC) OPERATORS IN MARITIME CONTEXTS

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Keywords: Functional Resonance Analysis Method, Autonomous ship operations, Remote operations, Skill Requirements

Introduction: Skill requirements for operators in remote operation centers (ROCs) of autonomous ship operations could differ from those for captains and navigators on actual ships. A significant issue, in this context, is what specific skills and how much of those skills are required for those remote operators. The purpose of this research is to reveal the skill requirements for the remote operators. In particular, we conducted a series of analyzes to envision the nature of the remote operation by using Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) and highlight the difference between the tasks on the actual ships and ROC.

Methods: We firstly developed a “work-as-imagined” FRAM model of the remote operations based on a research paper [1]. Then we conducted an experiment by setting up a pseudo-ROC to simulate the remote operation environment. In the end, a “work-to-be-done” FRAM model of the remote operations was developed to figure out the nature of remote operations and requirements for the human operators responsible for the tasks in the ROC.

Results and Discussion: The first “work-as-imagined” FRAM model of the remote operations suggested that the majority part of the operation is controlled by the autonomous ship navigation system described in the paper, and human operators are supposed to take part in the operation only when some alarms or alerts are launched, leading to poor situation awareness and excessive workloads during the monitoring. In the following experiment, the result found that the information required for the monitoring task is quite limited, and it was hard for the participants to understand the actual situation sea. In the end, the result of the experiment was adopted to update the FRAM model, which proposes more active involvement of human operators in operations.

Conclusion: The analysis found that the nature of tasks in the ROC and on the actual ships is different in terms of the involvement in the operations. Although this result may seem obvious, it is still difficult for many of us to be aware of these issues without any prior knowledge or detailed

explanation. The FRAM model provides insights to understand them, and this research will go on to reveal further details of skill requirements for the remote operators.

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FUNCTIONAL PATTERNS FROM INSTANTIATIONS

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Keywords: FRAM, Data Mining

Introduction: Market basket analysis is a common investigation in the field of data mining (and machine learning). The goal is to “mine” a dataset of consumer purchases (or their baskets) for trends that can represent consumer buying patterns. By understanding or suggesting consumer buying patterns, companies are able to promote cross-selling of products which can improve total sales and/or profits. For example, when you buy a product online the website will suggest “other products that you may like.” The suggestion is typically made by performing market basket analysis on consumer purchasing data.

If this approach can be an effective analysis tool for investigation of a complex system such as, consumer buying patterns, it could also provide value by being added to the FRAM analyst's tool kit. While consumer buying patterns are assessed in market basket analysis for a purchasing dataset and used as a basis for business management, a similar thing could be done for FRAM models by using a functional signature (instantiation) dataset. If the dataset is generated for functional data, a similar analysis can be performed to assess “functional patterns” that can be linked to different levels of system performance. If “strong patterns” are identified, the information may be used to help manage the system.

Methods: This approach aims to integrate the FRAM and Data Mining. The concept of a functional signature [1] can be used to determine suitable and/or possible metrics related to the system's functionality. A measure(s) of system performance should be defined that is related to the overall goal(s) of the system. Each function has (at least) three pieces of information that can be used to record the variability in an instantiation: 1) the function's output, 2) the time to execute the function, and 3) whether a function is active during the instantiation. This information accounts for functional variability as per the functional signature concept. Once appropriate metrics are defined, data could be

actively or passively collected to build a database of functional signatures, which represent the functional details that are associated with corresponding system performance measurements. Over time the database can grow and become richer in data, then data mining can be used to mine for potential functional patterns.

Data mining is a broad subject with a variety of tools. This initial proposal will focus on the use of two specific tools from the field of data mining, classification/clustering and association rule mining. There are 3 significant steps required to integrate data mining with the FRAM:

- 1) Collecting and/or preparing the dataset
- 2) Classifying the relevant data attributes
- 3) Checking the association rules to see if functional patterns exist (or determine the “strength” of those rules)

Results and Discussion: This work mainly presents the approach conceptually. Results will be preliminary and for demonstrative purposes. However, implications and practicalities of applying the approach will be discussed by considering ways to prepare the dataset from the FRAM model, selecting metrics, relative sizes of dataset to the number of variables and classifications, and the determination of a “functional pattern” from association rules.

Conclusion: This approach is a data-driven way to investigate system functionality using the FRAM. It provides a way to dig deeper and investigate complex patterns that may not be apparent and/or comprehensible by human observation alone. This work is conceptual but demonstrates a novel approach to investigate functional patterns in FRAM modelling. The concept can be applied in more detail in future work to more fully understand its utility and limitations.

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